

Impact of habitat fragmentation on the Diversity of Flora and Fauna of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The overarching objective of the study was to assess the impact of habitat fragmentation on the flora and fauna of Bangladesh. It is revealed that both the population size and species richness decrease with the increase of habitat fragmentation. Small populations are more vulnerable to change events, which increases the probability of local extinctions. The migration rate of both flora and fauna is lower in the patches that are remotely located from the mainland or source population. Small populations also tend to suffer from genetic drift and inbreeding depression. The failure of animal movements in the fragment restricts the migration of plant species and their gene flows. It was argued that the natural old forests of Bangladesh are critically fragmented to the point where they are unlikely to maintain the rich level of biodiversity, nor support viable populations of native species of flora and fauna. The probability of local extinction of certain animal or plant groups is higher on the edges. Range-bound animals like Capped Langur, Royal Bengal Tiger, Asian Elephant, Western Hoolock Gibbons, Marbled and Fishing Cat have become critically endangered due to habitat fragmentation. The study developed an integrated management approach highlighting both *ex-situ* and *in-situ* conservation.

Keywords: Habitat fragmentation, edge effect, migration, local extinction, range bound, inbreeding depression

Introduction

The biodiversity hotspots of the globe contain a high degree of endemism and are undergoing gradual loss of habitats (Trew & Maclean 2021; Bellard *et al.* 2014). Most of the hotspots are located in tropical forests, which are considered endangered (Myers 1988; Cardoso Da Silva & Bates 2002; Hrdina & Romportl 2017). Habitat fragmentation is one of the major causes of biodiversity loss (Fahrig 2003; Fletcher *et al.* 2018; Ewers & Didham 2006). Habitats can either disappear completely or they may become degraded and/or fragmented, both causing serious impacts on biodiversity as well as ecosystem processes (Raghubanshi & Tripathi 2009). Loss of natural forests and the fragmentation of remaining areas into progressively smaller patches is a significant global trend (Echeverría *et al.* 2006, 2008).

Habitat fragmentation occurs in different ways, like in patches, in waves or in linear (Islam *et al.* 2017). Tropical deforestation involves the conversion of continuous forest to the remnant of forest patches set in a matrix of non-forest vegetation (Turner 1996). This manipulation of ecosystems has consequences on biodiversity at both landscape and fragment levels (Haddad *et al.* 2015). The altered microclimate becomes unsuitable for certain species by reducing the fragment size further, increasing mortality rates near the edge and reducing recruitment to their populations (Turner 1996; Kupfer *et al.* 2006). The tropical forest ecosystem is often characterized by a heavy dependency on mutualistic species interactions for its stability (Hagen *et al.* 2012; Blüthgen *et al.* 2006; Bond 1994). Many plant species in tropical forests are reliant on animals as agents of dispersal for either pollen or seeds or both (Ghazoul 2005; Wright 2003). If habitat fragmentation causes the extinction of certain important pollinating or seed-dispersing animals, this severely limits the regeneration of rare plant species and hence initiates an extinction vortex (Turner 1996; Rahman 2023a). Overpopulation pressure and widespread poverty caused massive forest fragmentation and biodiversity loss in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.* 2009; Rahman 2021; Rahman 2023a, b, c). In addition, the tropical cyclones caused fragmentation in the Sundarbans mangrove (Rahman 2023 e, f). The fragmentation accompanied by biodiversity loss is the main threat to achieving sustainability and green growth in Bangladesh (Rahman 2023 g, h, i, j, k, l). The study aims to assess the impact of habitat fragmentation on the flora and fauna of Bangladesh. Together with this, an integrated management approach was developed based on respondents' perceptions.

Methodology

The secondary data were reviewed to develop a conceptual framework for the study. Three focus group discussions were carried out incorporating the respondents from diverse stakeholders like foresters, conservationists, botanists, zoologists and environmentalists. A total number of 10 key informants were interviewed to understand how an integrated forest management approach can be developed. Content analysis was done to interpret the data.

Consequences of habitat fragmentation in Bangladesh

Population size, richness, patchiness and rarity

The respondents opined that both the population size and species richness decrease with the increase of habitat fragmentation and decrease of the size of the patches. Rare and patchily distributed species require a large range of specialist habitats. With the decrease in habitat size, patch size decreases. Larger patches contain more species than the smaller ones. Small populations are more vulnerable to change events, which increases the probability of local extinctions. The small patches receive fewer migrants from outside. The migration rate is lower in the patches that are more remote from the mainland or source population. Heavily fragmented habitats cannot attract and support larger species. The biodiversity of a fragment is influenced by the fragment size and degree of isolation. Small populations also tend to suffer from genetic drift and inbreeding depression.

Plant viability and migration

The respondents noted that the failure of many animal movements in the fragment restricts the migration of plant species as the animal plays the role of seed dispersers. Like way, the gene flow is restricted if the pollinators cannot move. If they do not like to cross open areas, they are unlikely to utilize fragmented habitats. Consequently, the conservation value of isolated forest patches gradually decreases. Migration is an important phenomenon for maintaining local biodiversity. In isolated fragments, the rare species cannot be rapidly replaced by other species because of a failure of migration.

Edge effect

The respondents admitted that fragments' edges are inhospitable to a majority of forest species. The probability of local extinction of certain animal or plant groups is higher on the edges. The deforested matrix of a fragmented landscape is often dominated by alien species because few of the native species are tolerant of the extremely exposed conditions in the cleared areas.

Habitat fragmentation and the introduction of exotic species decrease species richness and heterogeneity of the native species. The respondents added that the natural old forests of Bangladesh are critically fragmented to the point where they are unlikely to maintain the rich level of biodiversity, nor support viable populations of native species of flora and fauna. Encroachment, clear felling, illegal logging, lopping, shifting cultivation, zhum cultivation, urbanization, industrialization, agro-forestation, land use change and agricultural expansions are the major causes of forest fragmentations.

Range bound animals

The respondents pointed out that Capped Langur has become an IUCN-red-listed species due to habitat fragmentation. Once upon a time, the Sal forests of Bangladesh were their sweet home. They live in a group in a large range. They wake up at dawn but remain sleeping on the tree until the sun fully rises. They love undisturbed and continuous natural habitats. Habitat fragmentation is the major threat to the existence of the Royal Bengal Tiger population in the *Sundarbans* mangrove. They need large territory for roaming and preying. The respondents also added that the population size of Western Hoolock Gibbons is declining at a faster rate due to habitat fragmentation. Asian Elephant once roamed across Sylhet to Chittagong Hill Tract. Now it is the largest critically endangered terrestrial animal in Bangladesh. The major cause of the decline in the wild elephant population in Bangladesh is habitat fragmentation. There has been rampant habitat loss of Marbled and Fishing cats throughout the Sal forests over the past 20 years. They are secretive, elusive and arboreal and live on the top of a canopy for both shelter and food. Marbled Cat prey squirrels, fruit bats, mice and rats living on the canopy. These cats are even intolerant to moderate disturbances.

What to do in Bangladesh?

The core of 'The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)' is the promotion of an integrated approach to natural resource management on large landscapes and to biodiversity conservation through enhancing wildlife habitat and reducing habitat fragmentation. In this context, the respondents recommended an integrated approach which focuses the following issues.

- a) introducing biological corridors;
- b) maintaining buffer zones in between core and peripheral zones;
- c) preventing fragmentation of land blocks and ecosystems;
- d) developing restoration programme in conjunction with local communities;
- e) involving indigenous peoples and traditional communities in conservation programmes;
- f) strengthening forest monitoring, research and development, education, and capacity building to maintain a "cradle" of biodiversity within the core areas of each protected forest;
- g) halting the continued introduction of alien invasive species;
- h) gap filling by rare tree species;
- i) afforestation and reforestation by native and natural species;
- j) facilitating natural regeneration in degraded forests;
- k) leaving denuded forest lands untouched for 20 years to promote natural succession of forests; l) stopping further clear felling and illegal logging;
- m) protecting natural regenerations (seedling, sapling and juvenile trees) from cutting;
- n) introducing pioneer and early successional species in the degraded forests;
- o) taking effective actions against the encroachers and land grabbers;
- p) establishing gene banks to conserve the gene pool of endangered species; and
- q) bringing endangered animals in captivity for breeding.

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